

NOTES

be preferably added near the equivalence point as a part of the indicator is found to be destroyed if added in the beginning. Some typical results are presented in Table 1.

Discussion

According to the method¹, the results obtained for quinone are 1.5-2.0% high. The high values may be due to the following possibilities. 1) The reaction between quinone and titanium(III) chloride may be slow. 2) The reaction between methylene blue and titanium(III) may be slow or 3) The reaction between methylene blue and titanium(III) may be retarded by the presence of hydroquinone. We have studied the reaction between quinone and titanium(III) potentiometrically under different conditions and have found that the reaction between quinone and titanium (III) is fast enough to carry out the estimation to an accurate value.

Preliminary studies made by us revealed that there is no effect of the presence of hydroquinone on the speed of the reaction between methylene blue and titanium(III) chloride. From the separate experiments we have found that the reaction between methylene blue and titanium(III) chloride is slow (which takes about 30 sec. for the disappearance of blue colour of methylene blue, when titanium(III) is added). Rao and Rao⁴ found that the reaction between titanium(III) chloride and the dyes (neutral red, phenosafranine and safranin-T) was catalysed by the presence of 0.1M overall oxalic acid concentration. So, we tried the effect of oxalic acid concentration on the reaction between titanium (III) and methylene blue, and found that the disappearance of methylene blue colour with titanium(III) is instantaneous in the presence of 0.005 M overall oxalic acid concentration. We have studied the effect of oxalic acid concentration on the reaction between methylene blue and titanium(III) in the range of 0.005 M- 0.05 M and found that the effect of change in oxalic acid concentration is negligible. We have found the similar observation in the case of cacotheline and thionine as indicators. Thus the high values obtained for quinone¹ can be improved in the presence of oxalic acid.

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Synthesis and Iodination of 5,6-benzo-4'-hydroxyflavanone

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IN continuation of our previous work,^{1,2} carried out in this laboratory, iodination of 5,6-benzo-4'-hydroxyflavanone has been studied.

1-Acetyl-2-naphthol and *p*-hydroxy benzaldehyde when condensed in the presence of potassium hydroxide gave a product which did not give any colour with alcoholic ferric chloride solution and a Wilson test³. 5,6-Benzo-4'-hydroxyflavanone structure, therefore, assigned to the above product. This was further confirmed on the basis of analysis of its acetyl derivative.

5,6-Benzo-4' hydroxyflavanone on iodination with theoretical amounts of iodine and iodic acid gave a mono-iododerivative which was converted into diiododerivative by further iodination with iodine and iodic acid. The same diiodo derivative could also be obtained from 5,6-benzo-4'-hydroxyflavanone with twice the amount of iodine and iodic acid. The diiododerivative on methylation gave the same product as obtained by the condensation of 3,5-diiodoanisaldehyde⁴ with 1-acetyl-2-naphthol in the presence of potassium hydroxide. Therefore, 3'-iodo- and 3'-5'-diiodo-4' hydroxy-5,6 benzoflavanone structures were assigned to the mono and diiodo derivative respectively. Triiodo derivative could not be obtained even with excess of iodinating agents.

In case of sodium salt of monoiodo derivative, when tested for the toxicity to fish⁵⁻⁹, the turning point of the fish¹⁰ was observed in 8 minutes while in case of sodium salt of diiododerivative the turning point was observed in 5 min.

Experimental

5,6-Benzo-4'-hydroxyflavanone (I), 3'-iodo (II), 3'-5'-diiodo-4'-hydroxy (III), 4'-methoxyflavanone (IV), were prepared according to the procedure described in the paper^{1,2}. 5,6-Benzo-4'-acetoxyflavanone (V) was prepared by heating the above flavanone (1g) acetic anhydride (5 ml.) fused sodium acetate (1.5g) for 4 hr. The reaction mixture was poured in ice cold water, and the product crystallised from glacial acetic acid.

The purity of all the compounds was checked by thin layer chromatography on silicagel, using benzene and ethyl acetate (85 : 15) as the developer solvents.

No.	Molecular formula	M. P.* °C	Yield %	%C		%H		%I	
				Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.
I	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ O ₂	241	21.7	78.86	78.89	4.955	4.498	—	—
II	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ O ₂ I	205	59	—	—	—	—	30.105	30.51
III	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ O ₂ I ₂	230	70.5	—	—	—	—	46.238	46.65
IV	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ O ₂ I ₂	173-74	80	43.01	43.24	2.548	2.34	45.62	45.76
V	C ₂₁ H ₁₈ O ₄	207	80	76.07	76.14	4.408	4.532	—	—

*All the m. p. s are uncorrected.

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Terpenoids. Part : CVI. A New Synthesis of 2E,6-Farnesol

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RECENTLY γ -carbon alkylation of β -ketoesters has attracted the attention of synthetic organic chemists because of their potential applications in organic synthesis¹⁻³. We have already reported the syntheses of some terpenoids^{3,4} utilizing this elegant technique. In this communication, we wish to report, based on the same approach, a new synthesis of 2E, 6-farnesol, an acyclic sesquiterpenoid alcohol, isolated from *Abelmoschus moschatus* Moensch and from other essential oils⁵. Structure (1) has been established on the basis of physical and chemical properties⁶ and syntheses⁷⁻⁹. The sequence of the reactions leading to the synthesis of title compound is given in chart 1.

β -Ketoester (II), obtained by selective alkylation of the dianion from acetoacetic ester³, with geranyl bromide, was converted into the chloride (III) in 65% yield with PCl₅ in chloroform. Chloroester (III) was reacted with lithiumdimethyl copper reagent¹⁰ to furnish, α - β unsaturated ester (IV) in 55% yield. The resulting product was purified by column chromatography over neutral alumina when elution with petroleum : benzene (4 : 1) gave (IV). The purity of the compound (IV) was checked by TLC which showed a single spot (ether benzene : : 4 : 1). The formation of *trans* product was confirmed through NMR spectrum

which showed signals at τ : 8.85 (3H, t, —C—O—CH₂—CH₃), 8.3—8.5 (9H, q, allylic methyl), 7.8—8.1 (11H, q, 8H allylic methylene and 3H, —CH₃ *cis* to —CO₂C₂H₅) and 4.7—5.1 (3H, m, olefinic protons).

Allylic methyl formed by the reaction of lithium dimethyl copper reagent on (III) is deshielded because of which it displays the singlet in the region where the allylic methylene protons exhibit the signals, thereby proving beyond doubt that —CO₂C₂H₅ is *cis* to —CH₃ and hence *trans* to the big group. Our results are consistent which those reported in lit.¹¹ Casey *et al* have observed that β -Ketoester when converted into the acetate in acidic conditions followed by lithium copper dimethyl reagent gave *trans*-product.

Finally, α - β -unsaturated ester (IV) on reduction with LAH in benzene¹² afforded 2E, 6-farnesol (1). The identity of the synthetic alcohol was established by